

Important Questions, About Which There Are Strong Feelings but Not Agreement

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On February 8, I moderated a panel on the war in Gaza at an APSA virtual research conference. To guide the discussion, I distributed in advance some difficult questions, about which there are strong feelings but not agreement. I continue to think about these questions and reflect on how they might best be answered. Here are my thoughts on several of the questions.

Some questions concerned frequently heard, but contested, words and phrases. “From the river to the sea” is one, and its meaning depends on the user and context. It might mean, as supporters of Israel charge, replacing Israel with a Palestinian state over all of historic Palestine.

Many Israeli leaders and others call for a Jewish state to be established from the river to the sea. Indeed, this was enacted into law by the Knesset in 2018. The phrase might also reference, as some Palestinians and Israeli post-Zionists advocate, the establishment of a democratic and secular state in the territory with equal rights for Jews and Palestinians. The word “genocide” comes up in this context. Criticism of Israeli policies and actions, however severe, is not antisemitism or advocacy of genocide. But is it advocating geno-

cide to call for Israel to be replaced by a democratic secular state, for the end of the Jewish state but not the death or displacement of Jewish Israelis? Advocating the destruction of a state, but not a people, may stretch the meaning of genocide too far.

And if the destruction or denial of a national political structure does constitute genocide, the term would certainly seem to apply to the Israeli 2018 Nation-State Law. This law denies Palestinians the right to a state. It proclaims that “the Land of Israel” is the historic homeland of the Jewish people and that the right to national self-determination in this territory is exclusive to the Jewish people. It adds that Jewish settlement is a national value and that Israel should act to encourage and promote its establishment and consolidation.

The term genocide may apply to Israel’s conduct of the war, although this will be fiercely contested. Israel is killing thousands of Palestinian civilians in Gaza, and objective observers claim that Israel has not done enough to limit civilian deaths. Israel has also destroyed or made unlivable the dwellings of more than half of Gaza’s population, forcing multiple displacements and, very probably, creating a new Palestinian refugee population. Given extensive media coverage, some will say we

are watching Nakba 2.0 unfold before our eyes.

Israel responds that it does what it can to minimize civilian casualties. Further, the staggering loss of life resulting from Hamas's 7 October attack, a loss equivalent to more than 40,000 American deaths, makes understandable Israel's determination to destroy Hamas. Understanding this goal, however, need not imply approval of Israel's conduct of the war, nor that its conduct is exempt from international law. Interestingly, and perhaps significantly, a recent report in *Jewish Currents* suggests that little about the suffering of Gaza Palestinians is shown to the Israeli public (Goldberg 2024).

Let me squeeze in mention of two other very controversial questions that I drafted for the APSA panel. The first is whether armed struggle is an acceptable form of Palestinian resistance. In the absence of other means to resist occupation and bring attention to their right to self-determination—an absence which, although denied by some, accurately describes the Palestinian situation—it is difficult to insist that armed struggle can never be justified. At the same time, while the legitimacy of armed struggle is recognized, at least in principle, it does not follow that killing and maiming civilian non-combatants, often with gratuitous brutality, is an acceptable way to advance the Palestinian cause.

A second question asks what should come after the war. American, Arab state, and other world leaders appear to believe there is no solution other than a two-state solution. How this could come about is, unfortunately, far from clear. Should this nonetheless be the basis for post-war negotiations, it will be important not to repeat the mistakes of Oslo, where prolonged negotiations consumed time

while developments on the ground made Palestinian statehood ever more distant. Progress around the table must be accompanied in real time by progress on the ground. ♦

References

Elisheva Goldberg. 2024. "What the Israeli Public Doesn't See." *Jewish Currents*, February 7. <https://jewishcurrents.org/what-the-israeli-public-doesnt-see>.